

Research Article

Music Harmony and Healing

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Received: 08 Aug 2024

Accepted: 12 Aug 2024

Published: 16 Aug 2024

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Introduction

In previous articles I have attempted to use other disciplines such as art and architecture to re-adapt healthcare providers in resisting the programmed medical response to training. Below we will review the neurology of music and add this to our arsenal of non-dominant hemispheric tools to revision healthcare.

"Music is the shorthand of emotion."

"He who hears music feels his solitude peopled all at once."

"Robert Browning"

Harmony in music and in healing

Socrates suggests that musical training and physical training are crafts of divine origin for the strengthening and balancing of two distinct sources of motivation in the human soul, one "philosophical" (wisdom-loving) and the other "spirited."

What is noteworthy is the metaphor through which he integrates the various elements of education they have considered so far. It is as if each guardian-in-training were a lyre with strings in need of adjustment – tightening here, loosening there – the goal being harmony in the soul.

Education in music and poetry stimulates and refines one aspect of the soul. Physical training stimulates and refines another aspect.

Both aspects matter. The result of an education that carefully harmonizes both is a person who is courageous without being savage, and sensitive to beauty without being enfeebled through over-refinement.

Harmony and soul are often discussed in the context of music, art, and personal well-being, emphasizing the interconnectedness of emotional expression and aesthetic experience.

Harmony

In music, harmony refers to the combination of different musical notes played or sung simultaneously to produce a pleasing sound. It is fundamental in creating depth and richness in compositions, influencing the emotional response of listeners. Harmony can be simple, like a major chord, or complex, involving intricate arrangements and progressions. In a broader sense, harmony can also refer to balance and agreement in various aspects of life, including relationships, communities, and personal well-being. Achieving harmony often involves understanding and integrating different perspectives and elements to create a cohesive whole.

Soul

The concept of "soul" can be interpreted in various ways, depending on cultural, philosophical, and spiritual contexts. In music, "soul" often refers to a genre that combines elements of rhythm and blues, gospel, and jazz, characterized by its emotional intensity and expressive vocals. Artists in this genre convey deep feelings, often reflecting personal and collective experiences. Philosophically and spiritually, the soul is considered the essence of a person, embodying their consciousness, emotions, and individuality. Discussions about the soul often explore themes of identity, purpose, and connection to something greater than oneself.

Interconnection

The interplay between harmony and soul is significant in both music and life. Harmonious relationships and environments can nourish the soul, fostering creativity and emotional expression. Conversely, a soulful approach to life—embracing authenticity and emotional depth—can lead to greater harmony in interactions and experiences. Both harmony and soul are vital concepts that enrich our understanding of music, art, and personal connections, emphasizing the importance of balance and emotional expression in creating meaningful experiences.

Bringing these ideas to a new model for integrative healthcare allows for different parts of the brain to be involved in the healing process (as dis-

cussed in the work of ian McGilchrist's rt/lr hemispheric functions in my earlier article).

Harmony can significantly impact mental health by fostering balance and well-being across various aspects of life. Here are some ways harmony influences mental health:

Holistic Well-Being

Harmony in life can be achieved by balancing physical and mental health. Engaging in regular physical activity not only improves physical fitness but also enhances mental resilience and emotional health by releasing endorphins, which serve as natural mood boosters. Additionally, managing stress and practicing mindfulness can cultivate inner peace, further safeguarding physical health.

Self-Esteem and Psychological Well-Being

Harmony psychiatric care emphasizes promoting balance in life, which includes addressing self-esteem issues. Therapy, mindfulness, and self-care practices such as meditation and exercise can help improve self-esteem and overall psychological well-being. This holistic approach aids individuals in managing emotions and thoughts healthily, contributing to better mental health.

Yin Yang Balance

The ancient Chinese philosophy of yin yang highlights the importance of balancing opposing forces within oneself. Achieving harmony between introspection (yin) and action (yang) is crucial for optimal mental well-being. Emotional resilience, cognitive processes, and social connections can all benefit from maintaining this balance, preventing issues such as depression, anxiety, and burnout.

Family and Social Support

Family harmony has been shown to positively influence happiness and mental health. Strong family support, communication, and emotional connections contribute to increased happiness and resilience, highlighting the importance of harmonious relationships in mental well-being.

Harmony impacts mental health by promoting balance in physical and emotional aspects, enhancing self-esteem, fostering supportive relationships, and integrating holistic practices. These elements collectively contribute to improved mental health and overall life satisfaction.

The importance of harmony in music extends beyond aesthetic pleasure; it plays a crucial role in emotional and psychological well-being. Here are several key aspects of how harmony and music contribute to mental health:

Emotional Expression

Harmony in music allows for the expression of complex emotions. Different harmonic progressions can evoke various feelings, from joy to sadness. This emotional resonance can help listeners process their own feelings and experiences, providing a therapeutic outlet for emotional expression.

Stress Reduction

Listening to harmonious music can significantly reduce stress and anxiety levels. Studies have shown that music with a soothing harmonic structure can lower cortisol levels, promoting relaxation and a sense of calm. This effect can be particularly beneficial in stressful environments, aiding in mental health management.

Social Connection

Music often serves as a medium for social interaction. Participating in musical activities, such as singing in a choir or playing in a band, fosters a sense of community and belonging. These social connections are vital for emotional support and can enhance overall mental health.

Cognitive Benefits

Engaging with music, whether through listening or playing an instrument, can improve cognitive functions such as memory and attention. The complexity of harmonies requires active engagement, which can enhance brain function and promote mental agility.

Mindfulness and Presence

Music can facilitate mindfulness, helping individuals focus on the present moment. The act of listening to harmonious music can draw attention away from negative thoughts and promote a state of mindfulness, which is beneficial for mental health.

Therapeutic Applications

Music therapy utilizes the principles of harmony to address various mental health issues. Therapists often use harmonious music to help clients explore emotions, improve communication skills, and foster relaxation. This therapeutic approach can be particularly effective for individuals dealing with trauma, anxiety, and depression.

History

The origins of harmony in music can be traced back to ancient civilizations, where the concept of combining different sounds to create a pleasing auditory experience began to develop. Here are some key points about the origins and development of harmony:

Ancient Beginnings

The origins of harmony can be linked to ancient Greek music theory, where philosophers like Pythagoras explored the mathematical relationships between musical notes. The Greeks understood harmony as the combination of different pitches to create consonance and dissonance, laying the groundwork for Western harmonic theory.

Pythagoras is known for developing a tuning system based on mathematical ratios. He discovered that the pitch of musical notes is related to the length of the string that produces them. For instance, a string exactly half the length of another will produce a pitch an octave higher.

This concept is part of the harmonic series and forms the basis of Pythagorean tuning, which uses simple ratios like 2:1 (octave), 3:2 (perfect fifth), and 4:3 (perfect fourth) to define musical intervals. Pythagoras also proposed the concept of the "harmony of the spheres," suggesting that celestial bodies like planets produce musical notes based on their movements, creating a cosmic symphony.

This idea reflects his belief in the mathematical order of the universe and its connection to music.

Medieval Developments

During the medieval period, harmony began to evolve with the development of polyphony, where multiple independent melodies were sung or played simultaneously. This period saw the emergence of organum, an early form of harmony used in Gregorian chant.

Renaissance Expansion

The Renaissance era brought significant advancements in harmony, with composers experimenting with more complex chord structures and progressions. The use of triads and the development of tonal harmony became more pronounced, influencing the music of the time.

Baroque and Classical Periods

The Baroque period saw the establishment of functional harmony, characterized by the use of major and minor scales and the circle of fifths. Composers like Johann Sebastian Bach and George Frederic Handel were instrumental in developing harmonic conventions that became standard in Western music. The Classical period further refined these concepts, with composers like Mozart and Beethoven expanding harmonic language and structure.

Modern and Contemporary Harmony

In the 20th century, harmony continued to evolve with the introduction of new musical styles and techniques, such as jazz, which introduced complex chords and improvisation. Contemporary music often explores dissonance and atonality, challenging traditional harmonic conventions.

Overall, the development of harmony has been a dynamic process, influenced by cultural, mathematical, and artistic factors throughout history. It remains a fundamental element of music, shaping how compositions are structured and experienced.

Cultural Subjectivity

The difference between cultures and musical harmony lies in how different societies perceive, create, and appreciate harmony within music, influenced by cultural contexts and historical developments.

Cultural Perceptions of Harmony

Different cultures have unique approaches to harmony in music. Western music, for example, traditionally emphasizes harmony through structured chord progressions and tonal systems. In contrast, many non-Western musical traditions might focus more on melody and rhythm, with harmony playing a less central role. For instance, Indian classical music primarily emphasizes melody and rhythm, using drones to provide a harmonic backdrop rather than complex chordal structures.

Historical and Theoretical Foundations

The development of harmony in Western music is deeply rooted in ancient Greek theories and evolved significantly during the medieval and Renaissance periods with the advent of polyphony. This contrasts with other musical traditions, such as Chinese or Arabic music, which have developed their own theoretical frameworks and harmonic practices based on different scales and tuning systems.

Harmonic Complexity and Simplicity

Some cultures embrace complex harmonic structures, while others prefer simplicity. Western classical music often explores intricate harmonic progressions and modulations, whereas traditional Japanese music, for example, might focus on simpler harmonic textures, emphasizing timbre and silence.

Cultural Influences on Harmony

Cultural contexts influence how harmony is used and perceived. In African music, harmony often arises from communal singing and the use of call-and-response patterns, reflecting social and cultural values. Similarly, the use of harmony in religious or ceremonial music can vary widely, reflecting the spiritual and cultural significance of music within different societies.

Overall, while harmony is a universal aspect of music, its expression and significance vary widely across cultures, shaped by historical, theoretical,

and social influences. This diversity enriches the global musical landscape, offering a wide array of harmonic experiences and interpretations.

In summary, harmony is a vital component of healing, influencing both physical and mental health. By fostering balance within the body, mind, and relationships, individuals can enhance their overall well-being and resilience.

Harmonic Medicine: Music and Emotion

Andrew Joshua Kobets writes: [1].

“Within the sound of your voice are the keys to innumerable worlds.” — The Hathors

Emotions transcribed to melody compel us to contemplate the consequences of music on our minds and our experience of the world.

Evidence shows that music can affect three hallmarks of human cognition: theory of mind, recursion, and abstract representation [16]. Although it was hypothesized early that musical ability resided in the right hemisphere and language capacity in the left, we are now aware that music composition, performance, and appreciation are complex processes regulated by expansive regions of cortical and subcortical systems. As previously discussed, data suggests pitch perception and relational tone awareness arise from the primary auditory cortex and its inputs from the thalamus and cochlea. Neuroimaging data shows that the other major component of music, rhythm, is perceived and produced in regions within the cerebellum, basal ganglia, and higher motor circuits [17].

However, how and where do the unity of such primary features create the emotional and cognitive experiences of music? Of this, Nietzsche said, “All possible efforts, excitements, and manifestations of the will, all those processes inside human beings, which reason subsumes under the broad negative concept of feelings, can be expressed through the infinite number of possible melodies” [18].

If one has ever experienced the strength of music, its chills and its joy, it is intuitively evident that music and emotion can be inextricably linked. Physical changes such as thrills, shivers, and alterations of heart rate can occur when listening to music, and neuroimaging data documents activation of the orbitofrontal and cingulate cortices, commonly thought to mediate physiological emotional response, during these physical changes [19].

When listening to music, dopamine is released onto the nucleus accumbens, an area classically thought to mediate reward perception and addiction [20]. Moreover, both “joyful” and “fearful” music resulted in stronger signal changes in the amygdala over emotionally neutral auditory controls, suggesting a dual role in an area once thought of simply as a fear center [21].

In fact, studies have demonstrated differential activation among the amygdala's individual nuclei and of the entire limbic system during emotionally suggestive, paired visual and auditory stimuli, respectively [22,23]. Despite this evidence, a melody's affect on emotion is not thought to be limited to neural circuitry. Prolactin concentration increased in the tears of patients listening to “sorrowful music” in one study, a hypothesis based on the findings that concentrations of the hormone are usually low in tears except during the immense emotional experiences of childbirth and orgasm [24]. The authors suggest the possibility that this property is part of an evolutionary mechanism for encoding memory during powerful emotional experiences. These discoveries beg the image of an orchestra activating an audience's prolactin concentration (in addition to its limbic, accumbens, and cingulate circuits) at will through executed melodic organization. Indeed, the fact that music activates such primitive and evolutionarily preserved emotional systems provides for interesting consideration as to its importance in the human experience.

Music and Memory

Just as we all have at one time or another remembered the words to an advertising jingle, music also can serve as a thread in the tapestry of a memory. In a study of recovery of cognitive function (verbal memory and attentional focus) and mood in stroke patients, those who listened to their favorite music daily had significant improvement in measures of higher cortical function, as compared to those who listened to audio books or nothing at all [25].

The role of music on implicit and explicit memory in patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD) has been investigated [26]. Interestingly, while explicit memory (song naming and judging a melody's familiarity) is impaired in AD, implicit procedural memory for playing a musical instrument was shown to be preserved in several patients with AD, one of whom had not played a particular instrument (xylophone) for more than a decade [27]. Apraxia (shoe tying) and ideomotor apraxia (hand waving) was even present in a few patients [27,28].

Finally, listening to background music has been shown to improve explicit memory retrieval on a semantic autobiographical memory task in AD, possibly through attention modulation and associative cuing [29]. This data is indeed exciting in its implications for music's effect on memory. Could the activation of music on the limbic system be mediating these effects? As we move further in our exploration, in what other ways will music serve as a preservative of the thoughts and experiences of our lives?

Musical Therapy

With influence over so much that defines our humanity, it is not surprising that many have looked at the means by which music can heal us. Indeed, music can be an inexpensive, powerful tool of medical care that is free of adverse effects and has a broad range of potential applications. Data showing stronger vocabularies and reading capabilities in children studying music (hypothesized to be caused by similarities in hierarchical syntax, tonal properties, and temporal qualities [32]) has led to music therapy becoming an adjunctive means to facilitate language acquisition in patients with learning difficulties and dyslexia [17,33,34]. In the field of developmental psychology, data suggests a medium to large effect of music on clinically relevant outcomes in children with developmental delay and behavioral disorders [35]. In adult psychiatry, a meta-analysis of active music-making, improvisation, and listening to music in an interactive

environment with a trained therapist showed improvements in emotional expression, motivation, global state, general mood, and negative symptoms, all of which followed a dose response correlation [36].

Pre-operatively, listening to a choice of different music showed decreased blood pressure, heart rate, respiratory rate, and State-Trait Anxiety Inventory scores, as compared to controls [37,38,39]. Post-operatively, patients given music therapy used less analgesia, reported up to a 50 percent reduction in subjective pain, had lower serum cortisol levels, and had decreased blood pressure, data that is consistent across a number of studies [40,41,42].

In patients with traumatic brain injury, rhythmic auditory stimulation increased gait velocity by 14.32 meters per minute, increased stride length by 0.23 meters, and led to greater gait symmetry than in standard treatment groups [43]. Post-stroke patients with a mean aphasia duration of 11.5 years who used specialized music therapy that focused on vocalization improved articulation, repetition, and comprehension to statistically significant effect sizes of 2.12, 1.29, and 1.36, respectively [43]. In a meta-analysis of five studies of insomnia (n = 170 patients), music-assisted relaxation before bed showed a standard mean difference of -0.74 (95 percent CI -0.96 to -0.52) for measures of sleep complaints vs. controls [44]. COPD patients who participated in 24 weeks of singing therapy had increases in maximal expiratory pressure vs. controls in one study (+3 mmH2O vs. -11 mmH2O) [45]. The authors credited this improvement to “a practical and pleasant way of training expiratory muscles.” Finally, back to developmental influences, 31 stable infants in the neonatal intensive care unit were exposed to either live, recorded, or no music for 30 minutes in an otherwise controlled-noise environment [46]. Thirty minutes after the end of the treatment, the live music group had a lower heart rate and an improvement in behavioral scores as compared to both the other groups.

Overall, these data show evidence for music's influence over a variety of domains in our practice ranging from patient mood, pain perception, language capacity, and sleep function, generally, on an overall sense of well-being. In our roles as healers, it is our duty to utilize all available means to treat our patients as effectively as we can. If an intervention as simple as providing them with music speeds their recovery or minimizes their discomfort in any way, even if only by placebo effect, then why would we not participate in this endeavor?

Music seems to permeate our experience as it intertwines with our thoughts and emotions. Nietzsche said that music “addresses itself symbolically to the primordial contradiction and pain in the heart of the original oneness, and thus presents in symbolic form a sphere which is above all appearances and prior to them” [18].

A so-called Mozart effect was first demonstrated in 1993 by Rauscher et al. showing that after 10 minutes of listening to Mozart's double piano sonata K448, a highly structured and ambitious composition, subjects improved their mean spatial IQ scores by 8 to 9 points [47]. The effect did not last beyond 10 to 15 minutes, but this finding correlated with EEG data that showed enhanced synchrony in the left temporoparietal and right frontal brain regions for a mean of 12 minutes in healthy subjects after Mozart's K448 [48]. EEG data even shows a 50 percent reduction in bilateral spike and wave complexes in patients with status epilepticus who listened to K448 for 5 minutes [49]. The effects do not appear to be limited to short-term exposure. Children who were given keyboard lessons for 6 months showed 30 percent higher scores on a spatial-temporal reasoning task compared to children who were given computer lessons or no training [50]. Finally, a large prospective study showed that cognitive leisure activities, which include the demanding yet graceful task of playing a musical instrument, could in fact reduce the risk of dementia [51].

It is hypothesized that the ordered structure of aesthetic sensory patterns can focus behavior and guide cognition, by which sound energy can manifest itself as physical changes modulating our perceptual experience of the world. Bringing such a modality to medicine is a noble endeavor, ever expanding a physician's repertoire to promote patients' health. If indeed it does work, its only limiting factor is the will by any member of the team to make it happen. The composer Virgil Thomson once said, "[w]hatever deceptions life may have in store for you, music itself is not going to let you down."

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Network Science and the Effects of Music Preference on Functional Brain Connectivity: From Beethoven to Eminem

Most people choose to listen to music that they prefer or 'like' such as classical, country or rock. Previous research has focused on how different characteristics of music (i.e., classical versus country) affect the brain. Yet, when listening to preferred music—regardless of the type—people report they often experience personal thoughts and memories.

To date, understanding how this occurs in the brain has remained elusive. Using network science methods, R. W. Wilkins et al, evaluated differences in functional brain connectivity when individuals listened to complete songs. We show that a circuit important for internally-focused thoughts, known as the default mode network, was most connected when listening to preferred music.

We also show that listening to a favorite song alters the connectivity between auditory brain areas and the hippocampus, a region responsible for memory and social emotion consolidation.

Given that musical preferences are uniquely individualized phenomena and that music can vary in acoustic complexity and the presence or absence of lyrics, the consistency of our results was unexpected. These find-

ings may explain why comparable emotional and mental states can be experienced by people listening to music that differs as widely as Beethoven and Eminem.

Listening to music affects an intricate set of complex processing systems in the brain, such as systems associated with sensory-motor processing as well as functional elements implicated in memory, cognition and emotion or mood fluctuation.

Listening to music often connects thoughts and emotions and, therefore, is associated with questions surrounding consciousness and "Theory of Mind" (the ability to understand the intentions and emotional state of others) However, little is understood about how listening to music affects the brain.

One of the most challenging neuroscientific questions surrounding the phenomenon of music preferences is how listening to different types of music can connect the same brain systems (i.e. similarly experienced circuits in the brain) associated with thoughts and memories.

Network science is a rapidly emerging and promising analysis method for investigating complex systems in terms of their elements and the relationships and interactions between the network elements.

The recent advent of studying the brain as a complex system offers a fuller understanding of brain organization and function.

In general, music seems to be handled by the right side of the brain. Brain scans haven't revealed any major anatomical differences in people who are tone deaf. It has taken more sophisticated tests to uncover some subtle variations.

An imaging and statistical technique called voxel-based morphometry calculates the density of brain tissue. In a study comparing amusics to people with normal musical ability, researchers used it to measure the white matter (which consists of connecting nerve fibers) between the right frontal lobe, where higher thinking occurs, and the right temporal lobe, where basic processing of sound occurs. The white matter of the amusics was thinner, which suggests a weaker connection. Moreover, the worse the amusia, the thinner the white matter. This finding is consistent with the notion that our brains use a "distributed network" when we listen to music. Their results show that across study participants high degree nodes, or hubs, were located in the default mode network (DMN) generally and within the precuneus particularly, regardless of song preference (Figure 1, arrows).

The precuneus exhibited consistent high degree across participants regardless of music preference. Despite being a high degree hub, compared to the Like condition, the precuneus showed relatively lower global efficiency in the Dislike and Favorite conditions. The precuneus has relatively low local efficiency and there was no difference across the 3 conditions. The scale depicts the percentage of subjects that has a top 20% node in each area for all three network statistics.

Previous analyses with fMRI and naturalistic listening have focused on brain network responses to specific components, such as timbral musical features and motifs, within a continuous musical excerpt. Here, they showed that when listening to complete songs, there are consistent patterns of network connectivity that exist within the brain that are related to preference.

Their findings reveal that liked, disliked, or favorite music dictates this functional connectivity, regardless of the type of music or the presence or absence of lyrics. The compatibility between our results and what music listeners frequently self-report in terms of neurobiology and neurorehabilitation.

We have shown that brain network connectivity patterns are associated with music listening and preference. These current findings indicate that regardless of the acoustical characteristic, functional brain connectivity states depend on whether the music is liked, disliked, or a favorite song. While perhaps everyone intuitively understands the mental experience or feeling when listening to his or her preferred music, whether it is Beethoven's 9th Symphony or Les Miserables, or when listening to their favorite song, such as one from Allison Kraus or Eminem, we show here that this similarity of experience manifests in the brain by engaging the DMN. As the first study to apply network science methods to 'real-world' music listening, these results provide a glimpse into the neural patterns underlying the emotion-cognitive states associated with listening to preferred and favorite music.

The Connection between Music and Health [3]

The ancient Greeks certainly thought so: They put one god, Apollo, in charge of both healing and music. Recent medical studies seem to confirm what the Greeks thought. Music seems to slow heart rate, lower blood pressure, and reduce levels of stress hormones. It can also provide some relief to heart attack and stroke victims and patients undergoing surgery. How does music exert these benefits? Some research suggests that music may promote the brain's ability to make new connections between nerve cells. Another idea is that it works its magic through its rhythms.

Humans are rhythmic beings: Our heartbeat, breathing, and brain waves are all rhythmic. The human brain and nervous system are hard-wired to

distinguish music from noise and to respond to rhythm and repetition, tones and tunes.

Music can help with stroke recovery. One study enrolled 60 patients hospitalized for major strokes. All received standard stroke care. In addition, one-third of the patients listened to recorded music for at least one hour a day, another third listened to audiobooks, and the final group did not receive any auditory stimulation. After three months, verbal memory improved by 60% in the music listeners, compared with 20% to 30% in the audiobook group and to the patients who did not receive auditory stimulation. In addition, the music listeners' ability to perform and control certain mental operations improved by 17%. The patients in the other two groups did not improve at all in this area. Music therapy also is used to help patients with balance and coordination. A program designed to train older adults to walk and perform various movements in time to music helped improve their gait and balance when compared with their peers.

Finally, music can relieve stress. It can improve mood, even in people with depression. And it can lower heart rates, breathing rates, and oxygen demands in patients who have recently suffered a heart attack. Music not only "has charms to soothe the savage breast." It also helps us to heal. The award-winning documentary film *Alive Inside*, which was released in 2014. It follows Dan Cohen, a social worker who is bringing music to people with dementia in nursing homes.

Cohen asked a documentary filmmaker to follow him around for three days to witness the astounding effect that music was having on the behavior, mood, and quality of life of patients who appeared to no longer have much of a connection to themselves and the world.

The filmmaker was so moved and impressed that he followed Cohen for months and created this film. Cohen's method is fairly simple. He asks a resident's family to list the songs or instrumental pieces the person once enjoyed. He then creates an individualized playlist on an MP3 player for the resident.

The music, which ranges from jazz to rock to classical, elicits surprising reactions. Some people, who had seemed unable to speak, proceed to sing and dance to the music, and others are able to recount when and where they had listened to that music. The music seems to open doors to the residents' memory vaults.

There is a growing body of evidence to explain why people in the film come back to life and begin to feel like their former selves when they listen to their playlists. Listening to and performing music reactivates areas of the brain associated with memory, reasoning, speech, emotion, and reward. Two recent studies—one in the United States and the other in Japan—found that music doesn't just help us retrieve stored memories, it also helps us lay down new ones. In both studies, healthy elderly people scored better on tests of memory and reasoning after they had completed several weekly classes in which they did moderate physical exercise to musical accompaniment.

Researchers at the music and neuroimaging laboratory at Harvard-affiliated Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center have shown that singing lyrics can be especially helpful to people who are recovering from a stroke or brain injury that has damaged the left-brain region responsible for speech. Because singing ability originates in the undamaged right side of the brain, people can learn to speak their thoughts by singing them first and gradually dropping the melody. Former Representative Gabrielle Giffords used this technique to learn to speak well enough to testify before a Congressional committee two years after a gunshot wound to her brain damaged her ability to speak. Singing has also helped healthy people learn words and phrases faster.

The sound of healing Music and healing once went hand in hand. The Chinese character for medicine includes the character for music. In ancient Greece, music was used to ease stress, promote sleep, and soothe pain. Native Americans and Africans used singing and chanting as part of their healing rituals. In Western medicine, the connection was gradually broken when the art of medicine gave way to the science of medicine. It's slowly being restored as music therapists demonstrate the value of music for treating people with everything from Alzheimer's disease to chronic pain and substance abuse problems.

Since 1980, researchers have turned their attention to the effects of music on the cardiovascular system. Most have looked at single variables, such as changes in blood pressure, heart rate, or blood flow through arteries. A few have looked at more holistic effects.

For example

- At Massachusetts General Hospital, a nurse-led team found that people with heart disease who were confined to bed and who listened to music for 30 minutes had lower blood pressure, slower heart rates, and less distress than those who didn't listen to music.
- Another nurse-led team at the University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee found that heart attack survivors who listened to restful music in a quiet environment for just 20 minutes were less anxious about their health than those who rested in a quiet room without music.
- At Abbott Northwestern Hospital in Minneapolis, men and women who listened to music soon after undergoing cardiac surgery were less anxious and reported having less pain than those who just rested quietly.
- At the University of Maryland Medical Center in Baltimore, researchers measured blood flow through the forearm (a stand-in for blood vessel health) as healthy volunteers listened to music or relaxation tapes.
- Blood flow increased significantly while the volunteers listened to music that evoked joy or to relaxation tapes and decreased while they listened to music that provoked anxiety.
- In a study from Hong Kong, older volunteers who listened to relaxing music for 25 minutes a day for four weeks lowered their systolic pressure (the top number in a blood pressure reading) by 12 points and their diastolic pressure (the bottom number) by 5 points, while a control group that didn't listen to music had no change in blood pressure.

Not all the trials have been successful.

Several found that music had little effect on physiological measures like heart rate or blood pressure, or on recovery from cardiac procedures. Contradictory results shouldn't really be a surprise.

One of the biggest hurdles to studying the effects of music on the heart is music itself. It isn't a single, repeatable "therapy" like a statin or stress-reducing breathing exercises.

Soothing music, like Debussy's "Clair de lune" or George Winston's "Moon," have different effects on the heart and body than something more rousing, like "Seventy-Six Trombones" from *The Music Man*, Puccini's "Nessun dorma," or almost anything from the Red Hot Chili Peppers. Music is also highly personal—what you find soothing might sound to someone else like fingernails on a blackboard.

One thrust of current research in music therapy is to see if specific sounds or tempos affect the heart regardless of the listener's musical preferences. Finding a relaxing melody that slows the heart rate, reduces blood pressure, and improves blood flow for opera buffs and rock-and-roll fans alike would make it easier to offer music therapy.

Music and the brain Like any sound, music arrives at the ear in the form of sound waves. The external ear collects sound waves, and the ear canal funnels them to the eardrum. As the waves strike the eardrum, they cause it to vibrate.

The vibrations are relayed along the chain of tiny bones in the middle ear until they reach the third bone, the stapes, which connects to the cochlea. The cochlea is a busy little world of its own. It is filled with fluid that surrounds some 10,000 to 15,000 tiny hair cells, or cilia.

Vibrations of the stapes send fluid waves through the spiral shaped cochlea. The fluid waves produce swaying movements of the hair cells. In turn, these cells release chemical neurotransmitters that activate the auditory nerve, sending miniature electric currents to the auditory cortex in the temporal lobe of the brain.

Functional magnetic resonance imaging scans (fMRI) in axial section through the brain of a healthy patient hearing the sounds of atmospheric music.

Highlighted areas show activity in regions of the cerebrum associated with hearing.

From there, things get even more complicated. Studies using MRI and positron emission tomography (PET) scans suggest that nerve networks in different parts of the brain bear primary responsibility for decoding and interpreting various properties of music.

For example, a small area in the right temporal lobe is essential to perceive pitch, which forms the basis of melody (patterns of pitch over time), chords (several pitches that sound at the same time), and harmony (two or more melodies at the same time).

Another nearby center is responsible for decoding timbre, the quality that allows the brain to distinguish between different instruments that are playing the same note.

A different part of the brain, the cerebellum, processes rhythm, and the frontal lobes interpret the emotional content of music. And music that's powerful enough to be "spine-tingling" can light up the brain's "reward center," much like pleasurable stimuli ranging from alcohol to chocolate. Although every healthy human brain can perform all the complex tasks needed to perceive music, musicians' brains are, so to speak, more finely attuned to these tasks.

At the other end of the spectrum, patients with brain damage may display remarkable defects in musicality; the noted neurologist and writer Dr. Oliver Sacks discusses many fascinating varieties of amusia in his book *Musicalophilia*. The neurobiology of music is a highly specialized field. But music also has major effects on many aspects of health, ranging from memory and mood to cardiovascular function and athletic performance.

Music and the mind

The most highly publicized mental influence of music is the "Mozart effect."

The "Mozart Effect" refers to the hypothesis that listening to Mozart's music can temporarily enhance certain cognitive functions, particularly spatial-temporal reasoning.

This concept originated from a 1993 study by Rauscher, Shaw, and Ky, which found that college students performed better on spatial reasoning tasks after listening to Mozart's Sonata for Two Pianos in D major (K. 448) for 10 minutes compared to listening to relaxation instructions or silence. The improvement was short-lived, lasting about 10-15 minutes, and did not affect general intelligence. The initial findings sparked widespread interest and led to exaggerated claims in popular media, suggesting that listening to Mozart could make people smarter, especially children.

This resulted in a commercial trend where Mozart CDs were marketed to parents under the belief that it would enhance their children's intelligence. Subsequent research has produced mixed results.

Some studies have replicated the effect, while others have not, leading to skepticism about its validity. A meta-analysis concluded that the effect size is small and may be influenced by factors such as arousal and mood rather than the music itself.

The effect is not unique to Mozart's music, as other types of music, including rock, have shown similar results in enhancing mood and attention, which can temporarily boost performance on spatial tasks.

Overall, while there is some evidence supporting a limited version of the Mozart Effect, it is not specific to Mozart's music and does not imply an increase in general intelligence. The phenomenon may be better understood as a result of the emotional and arousal effects of engaging and enjoyable music.

Struck by the observation that many musicians have unusual mathematical ability, researchers at the University of California, Irvine, investigated how listening to music affects cognitive function in general, and spatial-temporal reasoning in particular.

In their first study, they administered standard IQ test questions to three groups of college students, comparing those who had spent 10 minutes listening to a Mozart piano sonata with a group that had been listening to

a relaxation tape and one that had been waiting in silence. Mozart was the winner, consistently boosting test scores.

Next, the investigators checked to see if the effect was specific to classical music or if any form of music would enhance mental performance. They compared Mozart's music with repetitive music by Philip Glass; again, Mozart seemed to help, improving spatial reasoning as measured by complex paper cutting and folding tasks and improving short-term memory as measured by a 16-item test.

How might music enhance cognitive performance? It's not clear, but the researchers speculated that listening to music helps organize the firing of nerve cells in the right half of the cerebral cortex, the part of the brain responsible for higher functions.

According to this construct, music—or at least some forms of music—acts as an "exercise" that warms up selected brain cells, allowing them to process information more efficiently.

And in reviewing 16 studies of Mozart's music and human cognitive function, a Harvard psychologist concluded that the effect was even smaller, amounting to no more than 2.1 IQ points. It's a sour note, but it's hardly a requiem for the theory that music may boost cognitive function. In fact, the divergent results should serve as a prelude to additional research. And even if listening to music turns out to have little long-term effect on cognition, a 2010 review reported that learning to play an instrument may enhance the brain's ability to master tasks involving language skills, memory, and attention.

Music as Medicine

The biology of improvising

Dr. Charles Limb and Dr. Allen Braun of the National Institutes of Health conducted the study. Dr. Limb, who is an ear, nose and throat specialist, also plays jazz saxophone and is on the faculty of the Peabody Institute, the music conservatory at The Johns Hopkins University.

Limb and Braun persuaded six professional jazz pianists to play a keyboard while they were inside a brain-scanning MRI machine. The pianists

played a C-major scale. The scale is made up of only the white keys on the keyboard and is very simple for a trained pianist to play. The pianists also played a more complex original jazz composition that they had been given to memorize several days earlier. The authors then asked the pianists to improvise on the scale and the composition.

The researchers were particularly interested to see how the patterns of brain activity while playing rehearsed music compared to the patterns that appeared as musicians improvised. Indeed, the scientists saw a clear difference between the two types of playing.

Axial slice renderings of mean activations (red/yellow scale bar) and deactivations (blue/green scale bar) associated with improvisation during Scale and Jazz paradigms.

During improvisation, the medial prefrontal cortex (MPFC), which sits in the most forward part of the brain, became very active. Neuroscientists believe that the MPFC pulls together information that people use to achieve complex goals. In particular, these complex goals are the ones we tend to cherish because they are closely tied to our hopes and aspirations.

At the same time, the sides of the prefrontal cortex (PFC) were relatively quiet. This part of the PFC is more active when people are conforming to rules (as opposed to expressing themselves freely).

It monitors and inhibits inappropriate behavior. It also tends to become more active (and therefore lights up on MRI scans) during problem solving and conscious planning.

Since improvisation was also accompanied by changes in sensorimotor and limbic systems, it is tempting to speculate that these changes might be causally related, triggered in a top-down fashion by changes initiated in the prefrontal cortex. Increased activity in some of the sensory areas involved might be explained by their role in processing complex stimuli in the auditory modality.

Previous studies of music perception have reported both increases and decreases in limbic activity. Because of the presumed relationship between musical creativity and emotion, involvement of the limbic system was anticipated here. The deactivation of the amygdala and hippocampus we observed may be attributable to the positive emotional valence associated

with improvisation, consistent with studies that have reported these limbic structures to be less active during perception of music that is consonant or elicits intense pleasure.

However, they also observed more extensive deactivation of limbic structures in the hypothalamus, ventral striatum, temporal pole, and orbital cortex. The role played by these structures during improvisation require further study.

The idea of improvisation as a key component in the design and implementation of the new model of healthcare is critical as the players bring adaptive responses learned over decades and will need to “unlearn” reflex behaviours as we embark on this project. Improvisation and creativity and right hemispheric functions are key.

Music and the brain Playing and listening to music works several areas of the brain

Integration of Both Hemispheres

While traditionally, the right brain is seen as the creative side and the left as the analytical side, music uniquely stimulates both hemispheres simultaneously.

This bilateral engagement can enhance cognitive functions, language development, and social interaction. Musicians often develop the ability to integrate both sides, using creativity and logic together to perform and compose music effectively .

We have discussed this in my previous article as applied to art and architecture but does this apply to music?

Armed with the neurophysiology and imaging data reviewed above we can approach the need of integrating music as part of a new paradigm in healing.

Specifically in the spiritual non-left hemispheric interaction between healer and patient, I believe the use of this aspect of neural function will be vital in re-educating the resisting the normative adaptive responses in healthcare givers.

Spirituality, an innately human construct and force with pervasive influence across the expanse of human experience, organically and fluidly aligns with music as a similarly indigenous facet of human expression and experience.

When integrated, music amplifies and intensifies spiritual experiences such that new meaning for the client can emerge that transcends current modes of "being". Spirituality in turn similarly infuses music and musicking with a powerful and resonant meaning distinct from other music experiences.

Three theoretical considerations emergent from this integration – music and spirituality as experience, music and prayer, and therapist and ministry – will be explored with the intent to stimulate a discourse that can provide clinicians with concepts for inclusion in practice and researchers with avenues for future inquiry.

Key Aspects of Music Therapy as a Psycho-Spiritual Process

Integration of Music and Spirituality

Music therapy leverages the intrinsic connection between music and spirituality to enhance therapeutic outcomes. Music can amplify spiritual experiences, allowing clients to derive new meanings that transcend their current state of being. This integration can help individuals connect with their inner selves and explore deeper existential questions.

Palliative Care Applications

In palliative care, music therapy serves as a psycho-spiritual process that supports patients in integrating life experiences and finding meaning during terminal illness. It provides a framework for patients to engage with their emotions and spirituality, facilitating a sense of peace and acceptance.

Therapeutic Techniques

Music therapy can include various techniques such as guided imagery, improvisation, and songwriting, which are used to facilitate spiritual and emotional exploration. These techniques help individuals process their emotions, reduce anxiety, and connect with their spiritual beliefs.

Theoretical Considerations

The integration of music and spirituality in therapy is supported by theoretical frameworks that emphasize the experiential nature of both music and spirituality. This approach encourages therapists to consider the spiritual dimensions of their clients' experiences and incorporate these into therapeutic practices.

Holistic Healing

By addressing both psychological and spiritual dimensions, music therapy as a psycho-spiritual process promotes holistic healing. It helps individuals achieve a balance between mind, body, and spirit, leading to improved mental health and overall well-being.

Musical Medicine Melodies can help heal disharmonies in speech

A lesion on the elderly man's left frontal lobe, damage from a massive stroke, has robbed him of the ability to speak. The clinician sitting opposite him asks him to repeat a simple phrase: "Happy birthday to you." The man struggles, but only manages, "En oh en oh en oh" [6].

The clinician then asks him to sing the phrase. Holding his left hand, moving it rhythmically, she initiates the song. After a few attempts, she's silent, and he sings it as clearly as anyone carrying a cake with lit candles. The clinician then asks him, again, to speak the phrase. Without a hitch, he repeats, "Happy birthday to you." In less than two minutes, an extraordinary feat has occurred.

Yet for researchers like Gottfried Schlaug, HMS associate professor of neurology and director of the Music, Neuroimaging and Stroke Recovery Laboratories at Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center (BIDMC), such events aren't new.

Medical literature going back a century describes stroke victims who have regained aspects of speech through melodic intonation therapy. "The difference," Schlaug says, "is that now we have the neuroimaging tools to investigate what occurs in the brains of people who relearn language through song."

These tools reveal substantial overlap between areas of the brain that process music and language. Damage to the left hemisphere significantly impairs speech. And although the right hemisphere has some capacity for language, it responds best to clearly structured information, such as melodies. Layering language over melodies engages the right hemisphere's latent language capacity.

Schlaug speculates that when people cycle between singing and speaking, the melodic contour and continuous voicing enable the right hemisphere to vocalize words and phrases, creating a kind of language-smuggling Trojan horse. By moving the elderly man's left hand, the clinician helps him connect sounds to actions, sketching auditory motor maps into the right side. If a patient rehearses this entire process long enough, the brain's right side eventually compensates for the impaired left—and even changes structure.

“Ultimately,” Schlaug says, “we trick the right hemisphere into learning how to speak.” Neurologists once embraced the theory that the right hemisphere of the brain housed a person’s creativity, while the left hemisphere processed information such as math.

Musicians, then, should be highly right brain lateralized. In the early 1990s, Schlaug tested that theory. Using MRI technology to scan the brains of both musicians and nonmusicians, he and his colleagues discovered that the brains’ morphologies revealed the opposite.

Musicians, on average, were more left brained; those with perfect pitch were the most left brained of all. Schlaug has since focused on the planum temporale, which is part of the auditory cortex.

The planum temporale has a more pronounced leftward asymmetry in musicians with perfect pitch than in musicians without perfect pitch and in nonmusicians. “Professional musicians practice their skills many hours a day, for many years,” says Schlaug. “We think of musicians as auditory-motor athletes whose long-term training has an effect on brain function and structure.”

These findings launched Schlaug onto a trajectory of collaborations with researchers such as Psyche Loui, an HMS instructor in neurology at BIDMC and a violinist with perfect pitch, and David Alsop, a musician who is also an HMS associate professor of radiology at BIDMC. As Schlaug, Loui, Alsop, and colleagues use the latest imaging technologies to study the brains of musicians and nonmusicians, the unanswered questions mount. How, for example, does music affect brain adaptation, reorganization, and even plasticity? The team is also in the last phases of a longitudinal study on the neurobiological effects on children of learning to play an instrument. And finally, what about professional musicians?

Schlaug suspects they are not born with the natural advantage of an auditory-motor system that enables them to play a musical instrument. Instead, given the plasticity of the brain, particularly at a young age, their continued musical practice likely leads to brain changes that can be detected by modern imaging techniques. For many of us this is good news. “Unless you’re tone-deaf,” Loui says, “you probably have some unconscious musical abilities even if you can’t sing in tune.”

The flip side: Heads full of music Some people’s brains can’t process music, but others have just the opposite problem: brains that “play” music even when it’s not there to be heard.

Musical hallucinations are much more than the experience we’ve all had of getting a tune stuck in our heads: The music sounds real and vivid and not the least bit imagined to the person having the hallucination. Voices in combination with instrumental music seem to be more common than

instrumental music alone. People tend to experience familiar songs from their pasts.

Musical hallucinations can occur with other hallucinations and psychoses (breaks with reality). Several years ago, Israeli investigators found that a fifth of the 190 psychiatric outpatients they studied reported having musical hallucinations.

And there are scattered case reports of people with epilepsy having musical hallucinations during seizures. But people with no mental illness or brain injury have also been known to have musical hallucinations—and it’s the only type of hallucinations they have. In such cases, the cause often seems to be hearing loss. Sometimes there’s a similar phenomenon with loss of sight called Charles Bonnet syndrome.

People experience detailed pictures of familiar people and places even though their eyes aren’t functioning. One theory about musical hallucinations—and hallucinations more generally—is that normal sensory inputs inhibit traces of memory left in the brain. When people can’t hear (or see), the inhibition disappears, so the memory, in modified form, is experienced as a hallucination.

Music therapy as a psycho-spiritual process involves the integration of music with spiritual and psychological practices to promote healing and personal growth. This approach is particularly effective in contexts such as palliative care, where it can help patients find meaning and peace during challenging times.

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Cite this article: Julian Ungar-Sargon. (2024) Music Harmony and Healing. *Journal Of Neurology and Neuroscience Research* (5): 80-91.

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